

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LUBOWA****FIRST NAME: ERIASAFU****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID): Yes

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

1. Researching the topic (EUCLID 2024, 8)
2. Writing an academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 9)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34)
4. Writing in-text citations and quotations (EUCLID 2024, 34)
5. Writing style (EUCLID 2024, 40)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2024, 44)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

At first, I was nervous but also excited about pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). I was not sure where to start from. In the past six weeks, I have tried to familiarize myself with EUCLID protocols and all that is expected of me as a student. It is surely overwhelming at the start, with many documents to navigate and uncertainty about where to begin. On August 16, 2024, I managed to register and log in to the LMS portal. I have read through the documents sent to me and watched the 14-minute tutorial video that guide this research paper. I hope that I will do well and progress successfully. I have always assumed my English to be excellent, as it is the official language in my home country, Uganda. However, I have realized that I still have a lot to learn, unlearn, and relearn.

I have read the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period one revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2024). I also watched the ACA-401D basic tutorial video delivered by Prof. Cleenewerck on language, citation, and how to use paragraphs and headings when writing response papers (Cleenewerck 2016). I realized that learning never ends; there is always more to learn, relearn, and unlearn. To write a good essay, I must first be familiar with the basics of writing. I have established that even the smallest details, such as deciding to use UK or US English, are important in essay writing.

In this response paper, my discussion will be on five major concepts that I have selected to recap from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one. and basic tutorial videos. These will include researching the topic, writing an academic essay, plagiarism, writing in-text citations and quotations, writing style, and the Chicago Manual of Style.

The structure of this response paper is guided by the guiding materials, including a video on how to write a response paper developed by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma.

2) RESEARCHING THE TOPIC

Understanding how to research a topic of interest is important for any academic writing and research work. However, after grasping the topic, the next crucial step is to read and research what to write (EUCLID 2024, 8). Extensive reading and investigating of the subject matter will provide the writer or researcher with the knowledge and evidence needed to develop a thesis and answer the research question(s).

After reading the materials on researching the topic by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2024), I realized that while exploring the topic, it is important to keep specific questions in mind for which to seek answers. Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma emphasize that one should recognize what they already know about the topic, what they need to read and understand to write the essay, whether the material is useful to their topic or argument, and if they can use this material to support their answer (EUCLID 2024, 9).

In the same way, I must research the topic, Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma stress the importance of taking notes while reading, as this will form the basis for the essay (EUCLID 2024, 8). As I read, it is also essential to take note of keywords or sections by highlighting or underlining them. This will enable me to easily reference when returning to the notes.

I used to think that gaining a deeper understanding of the research topic simply required extensive reading. However, after reviewing the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one (EUCLID 2024), I realized that Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma were keen to highlight yet another important point. They emphasized that I should read extensively while keeping the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind, noting that it is crucial to use sound evidence to support my argument (EUCLID 2024, 9)

I learned that reading extensively alone is not enough. I must read extensively while taking notes and ensuring that those notes are relevant. This may take a little more time, but it is the right approach. Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma emphasize that I should spend considerable time seeking relevant information, such as direct quotes from texts, useful examples, summaries, case studies, or statistical data (EUCLID 2024, 9).

Additionally, I learned from Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma that even when I have the reading material at hand, the focus should be on the relevant materials and the content. They point out that essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking (EUCLID 2024, 9). With this in mind, I realized that I could not write a good essay without thinking critically.

After reviewing the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one (EUCLID 2024), I learned that having a long but relevant reading list, along with thoughtful consideration, is critical to successful research on a topic. In my opinion, if I do not have an adequate reading list, my understanding of the topic and subject matter is likely to lack depth and breadth. Critical thinking and creativity are essential throughout the process of researching a topic and writing an academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 9).

The essay should include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a topic (EUCLID 2024, 9). It should not only present evidence that supports my argument but also highlight opposing views.

The image below illustrates what Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma think about managing reading lists.

Reading lists:
If you are given a list of suggested readings, consult as many as possible. Otherwise, locate relevant material in the library. Use the catalogue to perform topic and subject searches. Once you have your readings:

- use the table of contents and the index to find relevant material
- skim through the text to locate specific information
- when you find something, you need to read closely, flag the pages with a post-it notes so you can return for a close reading
- photocopy useful sections of texts so you can underline and make notes.

Managing reading lists (EUCLID 2024, 9)

3) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

This chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one deliberates on the basics of essay writing. It clearly expounds on how to write a good essay, stating the preparedness needed in essay writing, the tips on essay writing, and the conclusion.

In a world where the demand for research-based evidence is increasing, academic essays are also getting more fame. According to the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack one, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, academic essays provide the answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence. As a Ph.D. student at EUCLID University, I will be writing academic essays. Thus, guidelines on writing academic essays will be very critical to me throughout the course.

When I am planning to write an essay paper, I should adequately plan how I am going to carry out the task at hand. I should commit time to the task. I should know what

am starting and ending with. I should have a writing plan as it helps me to be focused and organized in executing tasks before me.

The academic essay is aimed at answering a question or task. And for it to be effective, it should be backed up by evidence and example. In doing this, I must prepare accordingly by undertaking thorough research about the issue I am writing about (EUCLID 2024, 7). I should have a plan for how to approach the assignment and set aside time to understand adequate research to come up with a good essay. I concur with this argument because, many times, the subject being written about is not new, and I am not reinventing the wheel.

When researching the research topic, I will build on previous research; hence, a literature review is vital for me to write a good essay. It is important for me to take notes while researching because when drafting my paper, the information may be useful. The key to note is that when taking notes, I should write the sources, such as the author, publisher, and date of publication, so that such information will be used in referencing.

Also, important to note is that an essay should have structure to follow. I should structure my essay to communicate my ideas and answer the question. For EUCLID, the accepted structure should have an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10). A good structure makes the essay look organized and communicates it in an orderly manner. I believe it will also promote uniformity and help the lecturers and professors when reviewing my work.

When writing an essay, I should understand the requirements of the task at hand. I should understand the task/assignment at hand so that even when I know what I am researching, I will end up with a lot of information that may not necessarily be relevant to the subject I am writing about.

After reading and understanding the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack one, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2024), I have noted that when writing academic essays, I should be clear on the English version I am using; otherwise, a lot of mistakes may arise. Hence, it is prudent to choose the version to use.

The ACA-401D period one-course pack (EUCLID 2024) and the 14-minute video (Cleenewerck 2016) gave me insight into what I should be equipped with if I am to become a good academic writer. Various perspectives in this source have addressed the queries I had in my mind on professional writing. I believe this will help me throughout my journey in this pursuit of doctoral studies and professional work. The video was practical, and I believe with practice, it will be useful for me during and after completing my Ph.D. studies at EUCLID.

4) PLAGIARISM

Throughout the journey of my professional development, I have come to believe that plagiarism is a bad act that affects the person committing the act and one whose work

is being plagiarised. According to the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2024, 34), plagiarism takes various forms. (EUCLID 2024, 34), provides examples of plagiarism, such as taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author.

It is ethical to give credit to a person whose writing you are referring to. This not only encourages the credited individual but also adds value to the write-up and motivates others to share knowledge. (EUCLID 2024, 34) emphasize the importance of always mentioning the source. EUCLID stresses that plagiarism is wrong and unethical; it is unfair to take someone's work without giving them credit, and it is a serious academic offense that can have significant consequences. This implies that plagiarism can be treated as a legal offense, which can lead to serious legal repercussions.

5) USING IN-TEXT CITATIONS AND QUOTATIONS

Some of the ways to credit other people's work in the essay and avoid plagiarism is by using in-text citations or quotations. EUCLID (2024, 35) explains that the guidelines for using in-text citations and quotations should be respected when I am writing an essay. ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2024), gives examples of how to correctly use in-text citations or quotations (EUCLID 2024, 35).

For short quotations, the content should be enclosed in quotation marks. Based on the knowledge I got from the reading material provided by EUCLID (EUCLID 2024), I thought of an example that would reflect good referencing in line with EUCLID's guidelines. "In Uganda, culture plays a major part in shaping the behaviours of children in school and in the communities. This influences people's behaviours during their adulthood" (Lubowa and Semuyaba 45).

Additionally, EUCLID (2024, 36) points out that long quotations should not be enclosed in quotation marks and should be presented as a separate paragraph. However, EUCLID also stresses that the author must give credit to the original author of the content being quoted.

6) WRITING STYLE

I used to think that when writing an essay, the writing style did not matter until I read the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2024). The writing style is an important aspect. A standard writing style will align the essay with internationally recognized standards for writing. It is very interesting to know that writing an essay wrongly will make it difficult to read and understand, and consequently, it may not be used by others.

“The selected writing style should be consistently used throughout the essay. EUCLID recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted” (EUCLID 2024, 40). EUCLID (2024, 41) recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) however, other internationally recognized Rules can also be used (EUCLID 2024, 41).

The guidelines on writing style are usually published and can be accessed through an internet search. EUCLID (2024, 42) summarized the elements that the writer should take note of. These include spelling (US or UK, manuscript layout, sentence lengths, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active or passive language), and structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, and trademark or branding considerations.

It is amazing to learn that an academic essay that does not meet the requirements may not even be given copywriting by the publisher. Most academic institutions, such as universities like EUCLID, have written guidelines for writing academic papers. They require that their guidelines must be consistently adhered to by the writer. However, EUCLID (2024, 42) mentions that freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication type that they work with.

From the 14-minute ACA-401 Tutorial Vimeo video that I watched, I now know that although EUCLID encourages its students to use US English, it also gives freedom to the students to use UK English.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, has enhanced my understanding that the Turabian style is part of the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). However, while reading the chapter, I found the requirements of CMS challenging to grasp. Differently, the content in the CMS Crib Sheet is specific and well-structured in Chicago style and usage (abbreviations and acronyms, capitalization, compound words, emphasis (italics/quotes), numbers and dates, and quotations); Chicago page formatting (title and text pages, footnotes, headings and lists, bibliography and tables, and table notes); and Chicago end/footnotes (authors and books, journals and newspapers, reports, and papers, references and documents, and Chicago bibliographies). Although I found these details somewhat complicated, if I follow them correctly when writing, my essays are likely to gain recognition.

Regarding spelling, I learned that Chicago recommends using Webster’s Third New International Dictionary and the latest version of Merriam-Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary (EUCLID 2024, 44). The CMS style requires that, when writing an academic essay, sentence capitalization should include the first word of a title or heading, the first word after a colon, and proper nouns. Furthermore, the CMS style emphasizes that the first time a keyword or phrase is used in the essay, it should be italicized, but subsequent uses of the same word or phrase should be in plain text.

The CMS style also guides how to handle block quotations. It specifies that longer quotations should be formatted as block quotes. These quotes should be indented from the left margin by the same distance as a paragraph indent. However, it is important to note that the length of the quotation may vary between different writers.

8) CONCLUSION

This session, being my first step in pursuing a Ph.D. in Measurement, Monitoring, and Evaluation (DME), has warmed me up and will set the pace for my progress. It is a very enriching experience to read the ACA-401D period one course pack and orientation documents and to watch the 14-minute tutorial video delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck. I found the video very interesting and will continue watching it until I master the EUCLID-accepted writing style. This session made me realize that I still need to learn and relearn many aspects of English to become a good scholar and writer. I am now ready to start from the basics.

REFERENCES

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